

Specific Characteristics of Legal Regulation of Work of Part-Time Workers

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Abstract: This article talks about the specific features of the legal regulation of the labor of persons working in the Vakhta method.

Key points: Working by the time method, payment of wages to workers by the time method, vacation periods, time settlements, forestry, energy facilities.

If it is not possible to ensure the daily return of employees to their permanent place of residence, and when the workplace is located at a significant distance from the location of the employer, shortening the period of construction, repair or otherwise reconstruction of production facilities, social and other facilities, population Work performed to ensure the use of production facilities in uninhabited, remote areas or areas with special natural

You can use the time method in the following situations:

- in forestry, geological research, communication and railway transport organizations;
- in construction organizations that carry out construction-assembly, at the same time, reconstruction-repair works;
- in the use (exploitation) of energy facilities;
- in oil and gas industry facilities, as well as in pipeline laying, servicing and repair organizations and pipeline transport organizations;
- development of deposits of non-ferrous and precious metals, coal and other natural resources;
- in medical, trade and public catering, transport organizations providing services to employees of organizations using the time method;
- construction and reconstruction of highways and other organizations.

According to Article 472 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, remuneration for the labor of persons working on a time basis includes the following:

- ✓ to pay for the work done on time;
- ✓ to pay for additional days off between periods for overtime worked on time;
- ✓ overtime pay and other payments stipulated in the labor legislation or other labor documents.

If a collective agreement, an internal document or an employment contract does not specify a higher wage, the daily tariff rate for each day off (interval day off) in connection with overtime work within the current work schedule, daily rate (a part of the salary for one day's work) is paid.

For persons working on a time-based basis, per diem for each calendar day they are at the place of work during the period of time, as well as for the actual days divided on the way from the employer's location (meeting point) to the place of work and back. Instead, a bonus is paid for working on a time basis.

Employees can live in specially organized temporary towns or other employer-financed residential buildings, dormitories, hotels, and other residences. Employees' residences are equipped with necessary equipment and household appliances, medical and household services are provided. to be organized condition. In such facilities, technical and household services are provided by employees of the appropriate shift.

In the case of time-based work, it is usually calculated for a month, quarter or other long-term period, but not more than 12 months.

The accounting period includes working time during the employee's stay, traveling from the employer's location or gathering place to the place of work and being on the road during the return, rest time corresponding to this calendar period. takes The accounting period includes working time during the employee's stay, traveling from the employer's location or gathering place to the place of work and being on the road during the return, rest time corresponding to this calendar period. takes

In this case, the maximum duration of daily working time for the considered period should not exceed 12 hours.

List of websites used:

1. www.lex.uz
2. www.legalcity.uz
3. www.constitution.uz
4. www.pravacheloveka.uz
5. www.norma.uz
6. www.advice.uz.